

THE PALACE OF KOK-SARAY

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Annotation: This scientific article was aimed to the study of historical sites, especially the study of Kok-saray. This article contains all the interesting historical facts about Kok-saray. It is symbolic that the magnificent Registan shown in the previous part exists as if by itself, separated from the city by squares and gardens, while the real center of Samarkand is located in the neighborhood and is closely related with Tamerlane's name - here was his Blue Palace (Kuk-Saray), here remains the famous mausoleum of Gur-Emir with his grave.

Key words: Kok-saray, historical sites, Samarkand, Blue Palace (Kuk-Saray), Gur-Emir.

Introduction: Shakhrisabz, better known by its ancient name - Kesh, was founded during archaeological excavations before the Muslim Middle Ages, and then rose and fell several times. This city belonged to the family of Amir Temur. No wonder this place is called Shakhrisabz: the city is really located on a green, juicy, heavenly land. Previously, his name was Kesh (Kash). The Spanish ambassadors who arrived at the place where Amir Temur was shed (August 1404) describe it as a “Big City”. The fortress walls and gates were built by order of Amir Temur and under his personal leadership. The length of the wall was about 5 kilometers, and the tower was a rectangular fortress measuring 770 x 1730 meters. The Spanish ambassadors carefully examined the buildings associated with the creative activity of Amir Temur. The buildings of that time have partially lost their original appearance and have come down to us in ruins, some of them were completely destroyed. That is why the real information of Clavijo, who saw it with his own eyes, is of particular value for the history and practice of modern architecture.

The ancient city of Shakhrisabz was built almost three thousand years ago. This place is famous for the fact that the great commander Amir Temur, better known to the world under the name Tamerlane, was born here. The historical center of Shakhrisabz is included in the UNESCO World Heritage List and is carefully guarded to keep it intact. Temur built the first palace in Shakhrisabz and became famous as Aksaray. Briefly describing his official appointment in historical sources, Temur built a magnificent building in Kesh, a huge porch for meetings of his office, a place for the meeting of the cabinet of beks with the cabinet of Tajibeks. He writes that he built two small porches on the left side, and on one side of the building he left smaller shelves for entrants. The largest building in the city is Ak-Saray, which is the ruins of the once beautiful temple of Amir Timur. In memory of the place of his birth, Tamerlane founded the palace, from which only ruins now remain, but they are impressive in their size and remind of the former grandeur of the building.

But there was Kok-Saray, or the Blue Palace, the official residence of Tamerlane ... but, apparently, he considered Ak-Saray in Shakhrisabz to be his real home - that palace was luxurious and grandiose, and Samarkand - acting and not big. Kok-Saray is the palace of Amir Timur (Tamerlane) that has not survived to this day in the capital of his empire - Samarkand (now Uzbekistan). Translated from Turkish as the Blue Palace. According to some sources, Kok-Saray was the main palace of Amir Timur in Samarkand.

The unexcavated remains of the ruins of the palace are located in the historical center of Samarkand, presumably in the eastern part of Kok Saray Square, next to the main building (high 15-storey building) of the administration of the Samarkand region, near the bridge over the Dagbit's street. In addition, more than a dozen Gardens of Tamerlane are known around Samarkand - country estates "chorbag", Persian quadrangular parks with a regular cross of ditches inside and a palace at their crossroads; most of the time they were open to commoners, the ruler sometimes occupied one or the other depending on his mood, and contemporaries considered these gardens a wonder of the world, but none of them survived. Timur took care of where to rest in peace and tranquility from military affairs, and used Blue Palace only to work. At the end of the 18th century, the palace, destroyed by wars and earthquakes, was restored as a residence of the Bukharian governor and the emir himself during his frequent visits to Samarkand. The most important element of Kok Saray survived and we will see it later next to Gur-Emir. Today it attracts the people around the world so millions of visitors come and see the remains of the palace.

Kok-Saray Palace was built by Amir Timur almost immediately after his ascension to the throne in 1370. Kok-Saray was a four-storey building with significant dimensions for its time. The walls of the palace were lined with glazed tiled tiles. The palace itself is on a hill. In those days, this elevation was surrounded by walls. A bit later, another palace was built near the palace - Bustansaray ("Palace Flower Garden"). The Kok Saray Palace was one of the favorite palaces of Amir Timur, of which he had several dozen throughout the empire. In the autumn of 1404, Amir Timur stopped in Kok-Saray for the last time before going to China (Ming Empire).

In November 1497, Babur stayed in the nearby Bustansaray. After the death of Emperor Timur, the palace was used by his descendants. It is known about the use of the palace by Ulugbek. Until 1868, the throne room of Timur, restored later, contained the Kuktash throne stone (blue stone translated from Turkish). During the 15th-19th centuries, on the throne stone of the Timurids - Kuktash, located in the palace, there were ceremonies of ascension to the throne of Central Asian rulers from various dynasties, from the Timurids to the Mangyts. Although Bukhara was the capital of the Emirate of Bukhara, the Uzbek emirs of Bukhara Haidar, Nasrullah and Muzaffar performed the coronation ceremony in Samarkand, on Kuktash. The last time the coronation ceremony took place in 1861, when the ceremony of ascension to the throne of Emir Muzaffar was held.

Later the Bukhara emirs of the Mangyt dynasty partially restored the palace. Views of the palace and its doors are captured by the Russian artist Vasily Vereshchagin in the Turkestan series. At that time the ruins of the Amir Temur Mint were also found. To date, only the Kuktash throne stone has survived, which is exhibited in the courtyard of the Gur Emir mausoleum. So, today

we can see its ruins- the foundation of the Blue Palace (Kok Saray). The palace itself (like the Bustansaray palace) was covered with earth after complete destruction and still remains unexplored.

Conclusion: The city of Samarkand and its historical, cultural, religious, architectural and archaeological monuments, including the remains of the Kok Saray Palace, are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List under the name “Samarkand - the crossroads of cultures”. It is considered as a second capital of Uzbekistan. Almost all international meetings and summits are being held in the city of Samarkand. It has been the center of education, religion and cultures for many years.

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